

AMIRÈS

**QUANTUM
TECHNOLOGIES
INVESTMENT REPORT 2025**

TABLE OF CONTENTS

03

Introduction
and foreword

04

Methodology

05

Key takeaways

06 - 11

Geography and
origin

12 - 13

Deal type

14 - 16

Product type

17

From insight to
action

18

About Qu-Test
and Qu-Pilot

19

About the authors

INTRODUCTION AND FOREWORD

The **2025 Quantum Technologies Investment Report** delivers a comprehensive overview of the evolving funding landscape within the quantum technologies sector.

As quantum technologies move beyond early-stage research and into an expanding range of real-world applications, the startup ecosystem continues to scale and mature. This growing technological readiness, combined with long-term strategic importance, has reinforced quantum's position as a compelling investment domain, sustaining strong and consistent Venture Capital (VC) funding inflows.

The report offers data-driven insights into how investment patterns are developing across different time horizons, geographies, and technology focus areas. It is designed to support investors and ecosystem stakeholders in navigating the market, addressing key questions such as: **Which quantum segments are attracting the most capital? How large are typical funding rounds as companies progress? And how does Europe's investment activity compare with that of other global regions?**

The report is based on **investment data collected in 2025**, reflecting the latest developments in a rapidly expanding quantum technologies market. Its purpose is to provide investors with a clear and reliable market overview, supporting informed and effective engagement with the sector.

As Europe continues to strengthen its role in quantum technologies, the insights presented also offer **valuable guidance for emerging companies seeking both private and public funding.**

Let's dive into the quantum technology investment landscape together.

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AMIRES, The Business Innovation Management Institute, z.ú.

METHODOLOGY

This report is based on an extensive collection of data primarily gathered from publicly available online sources. To ensure accuracy and reliability, all information has been systematically cross-checked against multiple reputable platforms.

Key sources informing this research include The Quantum Insider, Crunchbase, Infinity QD, and Global Quantum Intelligence, among others, which together offer broad coverage of the quantum technology ecosystem. Where information was not publicly available, subscription-based resources such as AMIPLEXUS were used to access proprietary databases.

The analysis focuses exclusively on venture capital activity. Internal investments by large technology corporations, funding raised through public stock markets, and non-dilutive public or governmental funding have been intentionally excluded.

For consistency across the dataset, all deals originally denominated in euros were converted to US dollars using the exchange rate applicable on the deal closing date.

All numerical data and visualizations presented in this report were produced internally by our team. The insights reflect the collective expertise of professionals actively engaged in quantum investment analysis and support.

Most figures highlight both the number and total value of investments completed in 2025. Throughout the report, the “number of investments” corresponds to the count of individual deals, while the “amount” represents their aggregated financial value.

Despite careful data collection, minor information gaps may remain due to the inherent limitations of publicly available sources. These gaps are not expected to materially affect the overall analysis or conclusions of the report.

KEY TAKEAWAYS

The review of quantum startups that secured private funding in 2025 highlighted important insights and emerging trends, providing a deeper perspective on the sector's evolving direction. Here are the main takeaways.

- 1.** Global Venture Capital investments in quantum startups surged in 2025, with **total funding reaching \$4.36 bln** and the number of deals increasing by 26%, signaling strong market momentum.
- 2.** **Private-capital investments in quantum tech firms grew by 125% worldwide from 2024 - 2025**, a demonstration of rapidly increasing interest in quantum solutions.
- 3.** European investors outnumber U.S. in leading early-stage deals, but the U.S. continues to dominate overall investment amounts.
- 4.** Quantum computing continues to attract the largest share of capital, while quantum sensing has rapidly gained traction, growing from a niche segment to nearly 15% of deals since 2023.
- 5.** Although hardware startups account for most deals, **software and full-stack companies capture the largest funding amounts**, driven by a small number of very large late-stage rounds.

Geography and origin

GLOBAL INVESTMENT LEADERS**INVESTMENT DEALS IN QUANTUM TECHNOLOGIES
NUMBER BY THE STARTUP'S LOCATION**

2023

2024

68

private investment deals in quantum startups were recorded globally in 2025, that's 26% more than in the previous year.

2025

Key insights

- European startups have the largest share of the deals.
- The number of deals per continent continues to grow steadily each year.
- In 2025, Europe's share slips just below 50%, mainly because of the increased number of deals in Asia, Middle East and Australia.

Geography and origin

GLOBAL INVESTMENT LEADERS

INVESTMENT DEALS IN QUANTUM TECHNOLOGIES AMOUNT BY THE STARTUP'S LOCATION (\$MLN)

\$4.36 bln

were invested in private deals in quantum startups globally in 2025, representing a 125% increase compared to the previous year.

The logos represent the companies that have received the most significant investments in 2025.

Expert says...

Europe was home to the largest number of private-capital investments deals in quantum technologies but continues to trail the U.S. in total amounts invested, including in publicly traded companies. The EU Quantum Act and upcoming European Competitiveness Fund will be essential to transform Europe's technological creativity into technological competitiveness.

Thierry Botter, European Quantum Industry Consortium

Geography and origin

GLOBAL INVESTMENT LEADERS

DISTRIBUTION OF LEAD INVESTORS BY ORIGIN IN EUROPEAN QUANTUM STARTUPS

Key insights

- These charts show how European lead investors dominate funding in both local and global quantum startups.
- Europe’s quantum ecosystem is largely self-financed, with Europe-based investors involved in over 90% of deals within the region.
- European investors also lead the majority of quantum investment rounds globally.

DISTRIBUTION OF LEAD INVESTORS BY ORIGIN IN QUANTUM STARTUPS GLOBALLY

Expert says...

The quantum ecosystem in Europe is still predominantly self-financed, as startups depend mainly on domestic capital and investors tend to reinvest within the region. This tight internal loop reinforces ecosystem stability, while also highlighting the importance of globally influential funds such as Quantonation and 55 North in elevating Europe’s global standing in quantum technologies.

Olivier Tonneau, Quantonation

Geography and origin

GLOBAL INVESTMENT LEADERS

EUROPEAN VS U.S. LEAD INVESTORS: DISTRIBUTION ACROSS FUNDING ROUNDS IN QUANTUM STARTUPS BY LEAD INVESTOR'S ORIGIN AND BY NUMBER OF ROUNDS
2025

Expert says...

Although European- and U.S.-led rounds are nearly equal in number, the real divergence emerges in the size of investments. For Series C–E, deals led by US investors average \$240M, compared to \$105M for deals led by European investors, indicating that US dominance is driven by later-stage, capital-intensive rounds rather than broader activity.

Cécile Perrault, Alice & Bob

Geography and origin

EUROPEAN QUANTUM STARTUP LEADERS

**NUMBER OF INVESTMENT DEALS RECEIVED
BY EUROPEAN QUANTUM STARTUPS
BY COUNTRY OF ORIGIN**

2025

The logos represent the companies that have received the most significant investments in 2025.

Expert says...

Remarkably, while Finland's IQM may top the charts in total funding, in terms of sheer startup activity, the UK, Netherlands, Germany, and France lead the way. These countries are home to NuQuantum, Quantware, Q.ANT, and Alice&Bob—startups focused on building scalable, industry-ready quantum systems that are attracting strong investment.

Robert Harrison, Patent Attorney

In our 2023 & 2024 reports, we highlighted European startups that had just secured pre-seed or seed funding. Two years later, many of these early innovators are now reaching major milestones. Here's the examples of their growth in 2025:

In June 2025, OrangeQS closed a \$13.8 million seed round, described as one of the largest seed checks in the Dutch quantum sector. With the 2025 funding, the company plans to scale up development of next-generation quantum-chip test equipment.

In July 2025, Quix Quantum secured a \$17.5 million Series A to build a first-generation universal photonic quantum computer, enabling prototype development, team expansion, and progress toward commercial systems.

Geography and origin

EUROPEAN COMPANIES TO WATCH

These early-stage quantum technology companies in Europe secured pre-seed funding in 2025.

Covering both hardware and software, and ranging from quantum computing to communication and sensing, these startups now have the means to speed up their research and development.

EUROPEAN QUANTUM COMPANIES THAT RECEIVED PRE SEED OR SEED INVESTMENT

2025

Pre-seed

Seed

Let's monitor their progress in translating their funding into products - these are the players of the European future of quantum technologies!

Deal type

PARTICIPATION IN PUBLIC FUNDING PROGRAMMES - HORIZON EUROPE

Horizon Europe (2021–2027) is one of the EU’s flagship research and innovation funding programmes, supporting highly competitive, excellence-driven projects across Europe, including in quantum technologies. Given its selectivity, securing Horizon Europe funding is a strong signal of technological quality and execution capability.

Our analysis focuses on quantum companies that raised private capital in 2025 and also received Horizon Europe support, while acknowledging that these firms may benefit from additional public funding sources.

Key insights

- In 2025, just over half of EU-based quantum startups with private funding also received support from Horizon Europe, down from 58.8% last year.

AMOUNT OF INVESTMENTS MADE IN QUANTUM STARTUPS BY PUBLIC (HORIZON EUROPE 2021-2027) AND PRIVATE FUNDING (2025) (\$MLN)

Expert says...

While private investment has scaled to over \$1 billion in 2025, public funding remains the ecosystem’s vital backbone. With 51.6% of privately-backed startups still relying on Horizon Europe, it’s clear that public grants provide the essential de-risking needed to attract commercial capital. Maintaining this synergy is critical; public support validates early-stage research, while private funding drives the scale necessary for Europe to compete globally.

Mika Prunnila, VTT

Deal type

INVESTMENTS BY INVESTMENT SERIES

NUMBER OF INVESTMENT DEALS MADE IN QUANTUM STARTUPS GLOBALLY BY FUNDING ROUNDS

2025

The graph includes both main and extension rounds for each funding stage.

AMOUNT OF INVESTMENT DEALS MADE IN QUANTUM STARTUPS GLOBALLY BY FUNDING ROUNDS (\$MLN)

2025

The graph includes both main and extension rounds for each funding stage.

Key insights

- After fewer pre-seed rounds in 2024, pre-seed deals grew to represent ~15% of all funding rounds this year.
- Overall investment amounts have increased across all funding stages.
- While the number of Series B deals changed little from 2024, total investment jumped from ~\$200 million to \$1,341 million.

Product type

TECHNOLOGY DOMAIN

INVESTMENT DEALS IN QUANTUM TECHNOLOGIES NUMBER BY TECHNOLOGY DOMAIN

2025

Key insights

- The number of deals in quantum sensing startups has surged, rising from 3% in 2023 to nearly 15% in 2025.
- Quantum computing and quantum communication remain the leading domains, with investments roughly doubling compared to 2024.
- Funding for sensing and components has tripled, reflecting growing interest and maturity.

INVESTMENT DEALS IN QUANTUM TECHNOLOGIES AMOUNT BY TECHNOLOGY DOMAIN (\$MLN)

2023 & 2024 & 2025

Expert says...

Once again, the biggest checks this year were written to quantum computing players like PsiQuantum and Quantinuum—it’s a clear sign that computing remains the main magnet for large-scale investment, far outpacing other quantum segments.

Gökhan Eris, TNO

Product type

QUANTUM COMPUTING TECHNOLOGIES

NUMBER OF INVESTMENT DEALS IN QUANTUM STARTUPS BY THEIR HARDWARE'S QUBIT MODALITY

2024 & 2025

Key insights

- Photonics and superconducting startups continue to lead in deal count, with superconducting showing steady growth while photonics and neutral-atom startups saw slight declines.
- This year, funding rounds exceeding \$40 million occurred across all major quantum domains—except semiconducting, which saw the sharpest drop in deal activity.

AMOUNT OF INVESTMENT DEALS IN QUANTUM STARTUPS BY THEIR HARDWARE'S QUBIT MODALITY (\$MLN)

2024 & 2025

Expert says...

Investment continues to concentrate in a small number of mature quantum architectures. Photonics has been among the leading platforms in total disclosed funding—often driven by a small number of mega-rounds— with superconducting and trapped-ion platforms also attracting substantial capital, underscoring that large investment rounds remain focused on established technologies despite shifts in deal activity.

Audrey Durand, Institut d'Optique

Product type

CATEGORY - HARDWARE, SOFTWARE OR BOTH?

**NUMBER OF INVESTMENT DEALS
BY PRODUCT TYPE (HARDWARE/SOFTWARE)**

2025

Key insights

- Hardware-focused products in quantum startups have been steadily rising and are now dominating.
- After software led in 2023, combined hardware-software solutions are now catching up to pure software offerings.

**NUMBER AND AMOUNT OF INVESTMENT DEALS
BY PRODUCT TYPE (HARDWARE/SOFTWARE)**

JULY 2022 - DECEMBER 2025

Expert says...

Looking at the data, a notable contrast emerges: hardware-focused startups are the most numerous, yet software and full-stack companies consistently receive the largest investments. The difference is particularly visible in 2025, thanks to massive rounds—\$450 million for software-focused SandboxAQ, and nearly \$600 million for full-stack companies Quantinuum and \$1 billion for PsiQuantum—which account for much of the gap between number of deals and total amounts invested.

Anca Albu, QAI Ventures

FROM INSIGHT TO ACTION

With these findings in hand, we are determined to strengthen the European quantum landscape. Our objective is to push the industry forward through a targeted plan structured around three critical steps:

01

Attract and connect

Attract and unite investors with publicly funded resources, forging connections between the worlds of public and private funding, recognizing their potential to complement each other.

03

Promote

Promote the Qu-Test and Qu-Pilot projects, tailored to support private companies in advancing quantum technologies.

Be sure to follow our [website](#) and [LinkedIn](#) to stay informed about the latest news, and success stories from these projects.

02

Introduce

Introduce investors to quantum technology companies by leveraging continuously tracked market activity and emerging trends, using insights from a proprietary database of 300+ actively monitored investors to highlight opportunities for targeted connections and strategic collaboration.

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ABOUT QU-TEST AND QU-PILOT PROJECTS

QU- TEST

The Qu-Test project aims to create a network of quantum technology testing and experimentation service providers across Europe. The project aims to upgrade, upscale and integrate the testing and experimentation infrastructures and associated processes for quantum technologies. The objective is to create open-access distributed testing and experimentation infrastructure to make quantum technology facilities and associated services available to clients in all 27 EU countries. The target is to validate the relevance of the testbed service offering and the robustness of the Single-Entry-Point processes through the implementation of industrial use cases.

1st Project kick-off in April 2023

Budget: 19 M€
Duration: 3.5 years
Coordinator: TNO (NL)

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QU- PILOT

The Qu-Pilot project aims to leverage existing piloting infrastructure across Europe to support the growing European quantum technology industry. The project seeks to establish RTO-driven pilot facilities that will be well-networked and interact with each other. The end goal is to accelerate the time-to-market of European industrial innovation in quantum technology and establish a trusted supply chain. Besides, Qu-Pilot envisions developing practical strategies in synergy with European academic and industrial players to provide the quantum ecosystem with a 'one-stop-shop' offering unique facilities, competencies and know-how available in Europe.

1st Project kick-off in April 2023

Budget: 19 M€
Duration: 3.5 years
Coordinator: VTT (FI)

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ABIMI specializes in the management of national and international research, development, and innovation projects, focusing on new materials, production processes, information technologies, healthcare, energy, and environmental sustainability. We offer consulting services to enhance the quality of life and competitiveness across Europe. We promote funding opportunities, disseminate information, organize events, and publish activities related to our core areas of expertise. Additionally, we offer storage and processing of data from research projects, along with research and development of innovative data acquisition, processing, and visualization methods to further improve quality of life and competitiveness in our regions of operation.

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